

Spatial Augmented Reality with a Laser Camera Prototype

Challenges and solutions:

Operators of heavy non-highway machinery (for instance snow groomers) face multiple challenges. We want to help mitigate some of these challenges with our prototypes. For instance, our laser prototype consists of a laser and a visible light projector, with which we can augment the environment around the machine by projecting cues from the laser and or the visible light projector onto the environment. We can project patterns at points of interest to aid the operators, or warnings around the machine for bystanders. To achieve this, we need to know the machine's position within its environment. Therefore, we use GPS data and a 3D map to localize the machine and link predefined cues to the current position. There is essentially no limit to the information we can project – from current speed to directional guidance. As long as the projectors can handle the graphics, we can display them.

In addition to our laser-projector setup, we also developed sensor systems with thermal cameras. These are especially helpful in low-visibility environments, such as mountainous terrain, as thermal cameras can see through fog, low light, or precipitation.

Impact:

Our spatial augmented reality prototype has the potential to aid operators in their daily work by enabling previously impossible forms of information visualization and making that information tangible. Combined with novel sensor systems, it can support operators even further – for instance, by leveraging thermal and LiDAR data in harsh environments to improve environmental awareness.

Figure 1: Environmental Laser Projection for Snow Grooming

KEY BENEFITS

Novel prototypes for information visualization

Sensing in harsh environments aiding operators

